

Therapeutic ketosis and the broad field of applications for the ketogenic diet: Ketone ester applications & clinical updates

Raffaele Pilla

Pharm D, PhD – St. John of God Hospital – Fatebenefratelli, Benevento, Italy

Email: raf.pilla@gmail.com

Abstract:

It has been recently shown that nutritional ketosis is effective against seizure disorders and various acute/chronic neurological disorders. Physiologically, glucose is the primary metabolic fuel for cells. However, many neurodegenerative disorders have been associated with impaired glucose transport/metabolism and with mitochondrial dysfunction, such as Alzheimer's/Parkinson's disease, general seizure disorders, and traumatic brain injury. Ketone bodies and tricarboxylic acid cycle intermediates represent alternative fuels for the brain and can bypass the rate-limiting steps associated with impaired neuronal glucose metabolism. Therefore, therapeutic ketosis can be considered as a metabolic therapy by providing alternative energy substrates. It has been estimated that the brain derives over 60% of its total energy from ketones when glucose availability is limited. In fact, after prolonged periods of fasting or ketogenic diet (KD), the body utilizes energy obtained from free fatty acids (FFAs) released from adipose tissue. Because the brain is unable to derive significant energy from FFAs, hepatic ketogenesis converts FFAs into ketone bodies-hydroxybutyrate (BHB) and acetoacetate (AcAc)-while a percentage of AcAc spontaneously decarboxylates to acetone. Large quantities of ketone bodies accumulate in the blood through this mechanism. This represents a state of normal physiological ketosis and can be therapeutic. Ketone bodies are transported across the blood-brain barrier by monocarboxylic acid transporters to fuel brain function. Starvation or nutritional ketosis is an essential survival mechanism that ensures metabolic flexibility during prolonged fasting or lack of carbohydrate ingestion. Therapeutic ketosis leads to metabolic adaptations that may improve brain metabolism, restore mitochondrial ATP production, decrease reactive oxygen species production, reduce inflammation, and increase neurotrophic factors' function. It has been shown that KD mimics the effects of fasting and the lack of glucose/insulin signaling, promoting a metabolic shift towards fatty acid utilization. In this work, the author reports a number of successful case reports treated through metabolic ketosis.

Figure 1: Ketone Ester significantly increased resistance against Central Nervous System Oxygen Toxicity seizures (D'Agostino D.P. et al., 2013 Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol. 304(10):R829- 36).

Keywords:

ketogenic diet, seizure disorders, traumatic brain injury

References:

1. D'Angelo G., Pilla R., Dean J.B. and Rampone S. Toward a soft computing-based correlation between oxygen toxicity seizures and hyperoxic hyperpnea Soft Computing: DOI 10.1007/s00500-017-2512-z (2017)
2. Pilla R. The ketogenic diet approach as metabolic treatment for a variety of diseases J. Epilepsy: 2:2 <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2472-0895.1000e010> (2016)
3. Viggiano A., Pilla R., Arnold P., Monda M., D'Agostino D.P., Zeppa P. and Coppola G. Different calorie restriction treatments have similar anti-seizure efficacy. Seizure: Feb; 35:45-9 (2015)
4. Pilla R., Held H.E., Ciarlone G., Landon C.S. and Dean J.B. Female rats are more susceptible to central nervous system oxygen toxicity than male rats Physiol. Rep.: Apr 9;2(4):e00282. doi: 10.14814/phy2.282 (2014)

Why W neurons decreases and C neurons increases in fever?

K. M. Yacob

Marma Health Centre, Kochi, Kerala, India

Email: yacobkm@gmail.com

Abstract:

As you aware, if temperature increases (Absence of fever) after 31 degree Celsius, Warm sensitive neurons increase their firing rate and inhibit Cold sensitive neurons as core temperature increases. As temperature drops, the firing rate of Warm sensitive neurons decreases, reducing their inhibition, and Cold sensitive neurons which respond by increasing their firing rates.

On the contrary to increase of temperature, in fever the firing rate of Warm sensitive neurons decreases, the firing rate of Cold sensitive neurons increases as core temperature increases. inhibit warm sensitive neurons. The temperature increasing and decreasing controlled by the brain. The firing rate of Warm sensitive neurons and Cold sensitive neurons also controlled by the brain.

When the disease becomes threat to life or organs, blood circulation decreases. Temperature of fever will emerges to increase prevailing essential blood circulation.

WBC and their products stimulate the brain to increase temperature by increasing the firing rate of Cold sensitive neurons and decreasing the firing rate of Warm sensitive neurons. And it acts as a protective covering of the body to sustain life.

There is no way other than this for a sensible and discreet brain to increase temperature.

If the aim of Cold sensitive neurons increasing their firing rates in hypothermia is to increase temperature, then the aim of Cold sensitive neurons increasing their firing rates during fever is also to increase temperature.

How can we prove that W neurons decreases and C neurons increases in fever to protect the life or organ?

If we ask any type of question related to fever by assuming that the Warm sensitive neurons decreases and Cold neurons increases in fever to protect the life or organ we will get a clear answer. If avoid or evade from this definition we will never get proper answer to even a single question

If we do any type of treatment by assuming that the Warm sensitive neurons decreases and Cold neurons increases in fever to protect the life or organ, the body will accept, at the same time body will resist whatever treatment to decrease temperature and blood circulation.

No further evidence is required to prove The Warm sensitive neurons decreases and Cold neurons increases in fever to protect the life or organ.

Keywords:

WBC, Cold sensitive neurons, Warm sensitive neurons

References:

1. Mitchell D, Labum HP: Pathophysiology of temperature regulation. *Physiologist* 28:507-517, 1985
2. Fever: basic mechanisms and management. 2nd ed. Philadelphia: Lippencott-Raven, 1997:467-78.
3. R.S.Satoskar, S.D.Bhandarkar, Nirmala N.Rege- Pharmacology and pharmacotherapeutics –Revised XIV edition, p.159, 160, 163, 170). “Our understanding of the neural basis of thermoregulation and fever is still rudimentary. In fever, the thermostatic mechanism is set at a higher level even though it is not completely deranged. The role of fever in the defense reaction is not clear.
4. Berman's Pediatric Decision Making (5th edition) 2011.

Anxiety on Primigravid Women Attending Antenatal Care: A Hospital Based Cross-sectional Study

Shrestha S, Pun KD

Assistant Professor, Kathmandu University School of Medical Sciences, Nepal

Email: sushshrestha@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Background: High levels of anxiety during pregnancy have adverse effects on mother and baby.

Objective : To assess anxiety on primigravid women attending Antenatal Care.

Method: Analytical cross-sectional study was carried out on the primigravid women attending Antenatal Care out-patient department of Dhulikhel Hospital. Perinatal Anxiety Screening Scale (PASS) was used to assess anxiety on 502 women. Data were collected through face-to-face interview using Systematic Random Sampling Technique from May 2017 to December 2017. Chi-square test was applied to test the association between selected variables. All p- values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Result: The mean (\pm Standard deviation [SD]) age of the participants was 23.17 \pm 3.9 years. More than half (57.6%) of the women were from the age group 20-25 years. Just above two-fifth (41.4%) of the participants were in the third trimester of pregnancy. Out of 502 pregnant women, nearly half (46.4%) of them were at high risk of anxiety. High risk of anxiety was significantly associated with age and type of family. However significant associations were not seen between high risk of anxiety during pregnancy and residence, educational status, occupation, husband's occupation and gestational period of women.

Conclusion: The high risk of anxiety on primigravid women was quite up. Anxiety during pregnancy was more likely to fall on younger women (age <20 years) and joint families in comparison to those women from age and above and nuclear families respectively.

Keywords:

Antenatal care, Anxiety, Primigravid women

Fetal skeletal anomalies – diagnostic ultrasound difficulties.

Mircea Onofriescu, Adina Tănase, Alexandra Tibeică, Mirabela Petică, Bogdan Toma, Huțanu Dragoș.

University of Medicine Iași, Romania

Email: mirceanofriescu@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Congenital skeletal disorders comprise skeletal dysplasias, dysostoses and reduction deformities. Dysostoses are malformations of single bones, alone or in combination. Reductions are secondary malformations of bones. These disorders begin to manifest in the early stages of fetal development. In view of the large number of skeletal dysplasias (over 436 known types), a nosology and classification system was developed that categorizes genetic bone disorders into 42 major groups based on their cardinal features (eg, radiological findings, molecular etiology, inheritance) to facilitate diagnosis. The lethal group of skeletal dysplasias typically has an earlier onset with more severe phenotypic features than the non-lethal group, thus lethal skeletal dysplasia are potentially more amenable to prenatal diagnosis. Diagnostic accuracy is critical, as it will significantly affect parental counseling and decision-making regarding continuation of the current pregnancy, as well as options for prenatal or preimplantation genetic diagnosis in future pregnancies. However, specific prenatal diagnosis of skeletal dysplasias still presents a considerable diagnostic challenge, not least because of their rarity. The ability to diagnoses skeletal dysplasias prenatally by ultrasound is important for perinatal management and prognosis since various dysplasias are associated with different outcomes. Because of the low accessibility to molecular tests, precise clinical-radiographic phenotyping remains the mainstay of diagnosis and counseling. We suggest that the tight collaboration between a local reference center with dedicated personnel and expert diagnostic networks may be a proficient model to bring current diagnostics.

Keywords:

Congenital skeletal disorders, skeletal dysplasias, pregnancy

A review of Neonatal Jaundice at a tertiary hospital in South Western Nigeria

Sobande OJ ¹, Lawal TA ¹, Tongo OO ^{1,2}, Akindolire AE ^{1,2}, Ayede AI ^{1,2}

¹Department of Paediatrics, University College Hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria

²Department of Paediatrics, College of Medicine, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

Email: oluseyesobande@gmail.com

Abstract:

Introduction: Neonatal jaundice (NNJ) is a common problem in neonates. It is the clinical manifestation of elevated levels of (unconjugated) bilirubin in the body and occurs in 60% of term and 80% of preterm neonates within 1 week of birth¹. Despite recent advances in healthcare systems and increase in levels of information and community mobilisation, significant neonatal jaundice requiring hospitalisation remains a major health challenge in the developing world.

Although a preventable condition, severe NNJ is still a major cause of Cerebral Palsy in Sub-Saharan Africa², thus contributing immensely to loss of manpower to death and disability³, putting a strain on already scarce family and health care resources.

Data from the records of neonates who presented to our neonatal unit with NNJ was reviewed to provide an update on the incidence, risk factors, common causes, treatment modalities and outcomes among neonates presenting with neonatal jaundice.

Methods: It was a retrospective review of the case records of outborn babies presenting with jaundice between August 2018 and February 2019.

Results: Fifty-eight neonates presented with jaundice during the study period contributing 35.8% of total admissions. The male to female ratio was 1.9:1. The gestational age at birth ranged between 28-42 weeks. Forty-eight (82.8%) neonates were term with a mean weight at admission of 2.8 ± 0.7 kg. Modal age at presentation was 6 days and time interval between onset of NNJ and hospital presentation ranged from 1 to 12 days.

The mean (SD) of Total Serum bilirubin (TSB) at presentation was $20.4 (\pm 7.6)$ mg/dl (range 8.7 - 42.7mg/dl) and average (SD) peak TSB was $21.0 (\pm 7.9)$ mg/dl (range 9.7 - 46.3mg/dl).

About 39% of the mothers of the 41 neonates with TSB of at least 15mg/dl had Antenatal care at a secondary healthcare Centre while of the 23 neonates who presented more than 2 days after onset of NNJ, 13 (56.5%) had mothers with a tertiary level of education.

About half of the babies had G6PD deficiency. One-third had a risk of ABO incompatibility and 6.4% had Rhesus incompatibility. Twenty-three (39.3%) had a positive sepsis screen.

All the neonates had phototherapy. Seventeen (23%) had double volume exchange blood transfusion and 7(4%) had treatment with Fresh Frozen Plasma. In-hospital mortality was 8% while 22.4% had neurologic features of bilirubin Encephalopathy at discharge.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the burden of Neonatal jaundice remains high. G6PD deficiency is the most common cause in our environment. Late presentation at health facilities is the most important risk factor for poor outcomes. Phototherapy and Exchange blood transfusions remain the mainstay of management, however, these are often technically impossible in resource constrained settings. Prevention of severe NNJ is therefore the choice means to curtail the perennial menace in resource limited settings.

Keywords:

Neonates, outborn, neonatal jaundice, bilirubin.

References :

1. World Health Organization 2010, Effective Perinatal Care (Neonatology) Module 4N.
2. Burton, A. (2015). Fighting cerebral palsy in Africa. *The Lancet Neurology*, 14(9), 876–877. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(15\)00189-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(15)00189-1).
3. Teeple, S. (2018). The Contribution of Neonatal Jaundice to Global Child Mortality: Findings from the GBD 2016 Study, 141(2).

Association between estrogen receptor gene variations and risk of ovarian cancer in Pakistani population

Tehmina Mazhar ^{1,*}, Dr. Asma Gul ¹

¹ Islamic International University, Department of biotechnology, Islamabad, Pakistan

Email: tehminaraja@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Ovarian cancer is the most frequent cause of death among all cancers of female genital tract. In Pakistan it accounts for 3.9% after breast and uterus cancers in adult females. Scarce data is available regarding epidemiology, clinical presentation and genetic risk factors of ovarian cancer in Pakistan. The aim of the present study was to assess the relative frequencies of major classes and histology subtypes of ovarian cancer and to evaluate the association between risk of ovarian cancer. We analyzed the relative frequencies and patterns of ovarian cancer through clinical information of 186 patients. The relative frequencies of major ovarian cancer classes were surface epithelial tumors (82.3% ; 153/186) followed by germ cell tumors (13.4% ; 25/186) and sex cord stromal tumors (4.3% ; 8/186). The most frequent malignant subtype evaluated was 'serous cyst adenocarcinoma' (41.9% ; 31/74) followed by 'mucinous cyst adenoma' (17.6%; 13/74) and 'germ cell tumors' (8.1%; 6/74). The most common benign tumor was 'serous cyst adenoma' (47.06; 48/102) followed by 'mucinous cystadenoma' (22.5%; 23/102) and mature cystic teratoma (18.63%; 19/102). We analyzed the distribution of genotypes and frequency of alleles of the ESR1 polymorphisms in 79 women with ovarian cancer and 46 negative controls. Both polymorphisms were genotyped by polymerase chain reaction-restriction fragment length polymorphism (PCR-RFLP). We didn't find any significant difference in the distribution of genotypes and allele frequencies of 397T>C and 351A>G single nucleotide polymorphisms between cases and negative controls (P>0.05). Frequency of the homozygous polymorphic genotype 'GG' of 351A>G polymorphism has observed to be very less in our population. In the present study we demonstrated an insignificant association between ESR1 gene PvuII and XbaI polymorphisms and risk of ovarian cancer in Pakistani population. However, a study needs to be performed on large sample size and further investigations are required for the confirmation and to determine whether the findings are generalizable to other populations.

Figure 1: The restriction profile of ESR1 gene PvuII (c454-397). Lane M: DNA ladder (100 b.p), lanes 3,4,9 and 10: undigested PCR product, CC genotype (homozygous, polymorphic), lanes 2,5, and 6: TC genotype (heterozygous), lanes 1,7, and 8: TT genotype (homozygous, wild type)

Keywords:

Polymerase chain reaction, restriction fragment length polymorphism, single nucleotide polymorphism, estrogen receptor gene